

screening detected differences in resistance levels more precisely. For example, in this and in previous field studies, Bogor 8 has always been more resistant than Bogor 1 and the other 10 Bogor lines (not included in the table). Also, Mudgo, whose greenhouse reactions to biotype 2 are generally similar to those

of IR26 (susceptible, as both have BPH 1 gene), exhibits more resistance in the field.

Insect pressure was extremely high at 95 DT in the field screening and only the highly resistant lines such as CR157-392-284, CR179-1-717, IET 5120, IET 5122, ARC 6650, ARC 14529, and

the photosensitive varieties Babawee, Rathu Heenati, and Ptb 33 were resistant.

More varieties and breeding lines with resistance to biotype 2 and with multigenic resistance to several biotypes need to be included in the 1978 IRBPHN.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deep water

Stem borer incidence in deep-water rice

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Studies on deep-water rice in Bangladesh in 1977 revealed a surprisingly high incidence of stem borers in the vegetative phase of the crop (Apr. to mid-Sept.). The investigations involved regular pest surveys of farmers' fields in deep-water rice areas and an intensive study of the population dynamics of stem borers in two fields in Keraniganj and Manikganj, Dacca district. Stem borer incidence was assessed mainly by dissecting individual stems (usually 100 to 200 stems), and

also by counting egg masses and moths.

Stem borer larvae were found in each of 24 dissections from fields in Comilla, Dacca, Faridpur, Noakhali, Pabna, and Tangail districts. In 71% of the dissections, more than 10% of the stems were infested; in 33%, more than 20% were infested.

At the population dynamics site at Keraniganj, from late June to mid-September, the incidence of infested stems varied from 20 to 38%; at Manikganj it varied from 36 to 47%. In a new deep-water tank at Joydebpur planted to the variety Habiganj Aman II, 52% of the stems had been attacked by early September.

In a quick survey of some deep-water rice areas in Thailand, Burma, and India, stem borers were the most important pest; more than 10% of the stems were infested in several fields.

The yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* was constantly the dominant species and appears well-adapted to deep-water rice. Larvae feed in the hollow section of the stem. Because this section is usually submerged, the activity is not reflected by deadheart incidence; some dissections showed more than 30% infested stems without a single deadheart. For that reason, and because rising floodwater can submerge deadhearts in a few days, early and midseason stem borer damage in deep-water rice has probably been overlooked and thus underestimated in the past.

We do not yet know the effect of high levels of early stem damage, but yields are probably lowered. With the manifold problems of using insecticides on deep-water rice, the yellow stem borer presents a considerable challenge to breeders and entomologists.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Adverse soils

Aluminum toxicity and phosphorus deficiency in acid sulfate soils of Thailand

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Broadcast rice with symptoms that resembled those described for aluminum toxicity were observed in the eastern Bangkok Plain (between Pathum Thani and Nakhon Nayok) in June 1977. Older leaves had an orange-yellow discoloration along the margins and sometimes between the veins. Most plants also suffered from

moderate to severe phosphorus deficiency.

This deep-water rice area (about 0.25 million ha) has moderately acid sulfate soils (pH 4.0–4.7). The symptoms were most noticeable with increasing

acidity (4.0–4.3) and plants were almost dead in a field where road construction had removed the surface soil and exposed the highly acid subsoil.

Rice in the area is broadcast after the first rains in April or May, but flooding

Chemical analysis of plant samples. Eastern Bangkok Plain, Thailand.

	Elements			
	Fe (ppm)	Al (ppm)	K (%)	P (%)
Affected plants	309	911	0.93	0.031
Healthy plants	175	171	2.21	0.069
Normal levels	< 300	< 300	> 1.0	> 0.1